

AI & ROBOTICS

AI & robotics will have a significant impact on society, values & human rights

EFFECT ON VALUES & PEOPLE

TYPES OF IMPACTS

VALUES AFFECTED

- Accountability
- Autonomy
- Equality
- Fairness
- Human dignity
- Justice
- Integrity of the person
- Privacy
- Security
- Solidarity

PEOPLE HIGHLY AFFECTED

- Consumers
- Disfavoured or 'excluded' people
- First responders
- Healthcare providers
- Inhabitants of poor countries
- Patients
- Recipients of insurance & social benefits
- Regulators & policy-makers
- Tenants (e.g. minority ethnic groups)
- The elderly
- Workers

POSITIVE

- Improve medical diagnostics
- Advance cybersecurity
- Improve decision-making via data analysis
- Enhance healthcare
- Improve elder care
- Advance language translation
- Improve voting security
- Introduce new forms of co-operation & inclusion
- Reduce repetitive tasks

DUAL

- Alter human relations
- Alter legal frameworks
- Alter moral conceptions
- Change understandings of personhood
- Create unintended consequences
- Intensify big data analytics
- Escalate surveillance
- Increase profiling
- Increase leisure

NEGATIVE

- Harm/threat of harm from autonomous weapons
- Loss of control over privacy & personal data
- Bias & discrimination
- Cyberwarfare
- Increase class/wealth domination
- Diminish media pluralism
- Greater energy consumption

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Technology, ethics and human rights

We will help address some of these issues by:

- Reviewing the legal, ethical, social & economic impacts of AI & robotics
- Connecting with citizens to understand concerns via surveys in 11 countries & panels in 5 countries
- Consulting experts and discussing ethical & human rights issues
- Developing ethical codes & protocols

